

Effect of Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time on Performance in Algebra among Polytechnics Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

Mukhtar, Nuraddeen¹

nuraddeenm142@gmail.com

+2348034987045

Hassan, Aminu²

aminuhassan729@gmail.com

+2348163705055

Uba, James Uba³

ubajamesuba@gmail.com

+2349037863905

¹Department of General Studies, Federal Polytechnic Ugep, Cross River State

²Department of Statistics, Federal Polytechnic Ugep, Cross River State

³Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria

Abstract

Performance in mathematics is regard to as global problem. This paper investigated the “Effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One research question and a corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Two public polytechnics made up the population of the Study consists of all polytechnic students in cross river state during the 2023/2024 academic session with a sample size of 44 students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. The methodology of the study is pretest and posttest quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The experimental and control groups were exposed to Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and Lecture Method respectively. The experimental group ware taught Algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time while the control group ware taught algebra using Lecture method. Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was designed by the researchers for data collection. The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. The data collected were analyzed using Mean scores, Standard deviation and t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant difference between performance of students taught algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method. Better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that lecture-enriched wait-time should be used to teach mathematics at national diploma level.

Keyword: Lecture-enriched wait-time, algebra, performance

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the school subjects with wide applications which can not be separated from our day to day activities. It considered as the universal language throughout the world. It techniques includes counting, arithmetic, mensuration, geometry, trigonometry, computations and algebra, with the ability to think about situations related to a given quantity (Cawley *et al*, 1998). Mathematics is a fundamental branch of Science that represents the study of basic concepts of Numbers, Space and Quantity as well as application of these concepts in the field of Physics and Engineering (Ale, 2006).

Poor performance in the subject area becomes of great concern to our society, educators and government at large. Nneji (2013), described performance as the gain in knowledge of students as a result of taking part in learning activity or programme. For effective learning to be efficiently taken, we need the right approaches and methods. There are so many devices for effective teaching and an effective technique can ensure effective learning. It is being felt that there should be new techniques of teaching and learning (Iqbal, 2004). The search of teaching and learning devices for effective performance has lead to the identification of wait-time (Lee, 2000).

Any behavior, practice or techniques that will enable students develop thinking skills will help them to acquire technology concepts, which will lead to better achievement. Hurd in UNESCO (1995) pointed out that the methodology for teaching must enable students to think and ask questions during classroom lesson. One way of developing students' thinking

skill is to ask questions in the classroom to facilitate discussion and to get the students to think (Adsit, 2002). There is therefore a good link between teaching methods and questioning. The importance of question cannot be over emphasized, question can be used by teachers in the classrooms to determine whether or not body of knowledge has been impacted and to determine how much has been learned. It can be used for evaluation of method of teaching and for students placement.

According to Baba (2022) wait-time is when a teacher waits after a question is asked before calling on a student to rephrase a question or supply the answer. Wait-time is the amount of time a teacher allows, after asking a question, before getting response from students (wait-time I). It is also a period of uninterrupted silence allowed by the teacher after receiving a student's response and before he/she comments or asks another question (wait-time II). Research has shown that for both wait-time I and II, teachers typically wait for an average of one second or less (Kissock and Iyortsuun, 1982; Ouyang, 2000; Cotton, 2001 and Camp, 2002). Increasing wait-time to three seconds or more has been found to increase students' achievement and interest (Stahl as cited in Owodunni, 2013, Rowe as cited in Lee, 2000 and Cotton, 2001). Opataye (2020), study the effectiveness of classroom questioning wait – time on senior secondary school students' academic performance and reflective thinking in chemistry, it was shown that, chemistry students that were given questioning wait - time performed better and with higher reflective thinking in chemistry.

Effective questioning is an instrument of motivation to raise the interest of students in what is being learnt (Eze, 2008). Raising students' interest helps them to learn better and most likely retain what is learnt for a longer period and subsequently, achievement would be enhanced. Owodunni (2013), investigate the comparative effects of long wait - time and shifting interaction questioning techniques on basic electricity students academic achievement in technical colleges. It was showed that shifting interaction questioning technique is more effective in enhancing students' achievement in basic electricity. There are different types of learners including fast learners, average learners, and slow learners (Korikana, 2020). This learning difficulty may arise from poor memory, unawareness about the importance of education and lack of fundamental knowledge and psychological factors

Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this research, investigate effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

As part of the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum, algebra is a core course for all sciences, engineering and environmental technology. Algebra as one of the studied areas that deals with the representation of problems or situations in the form of mathematical expressions. All the branches of mathematics needs algebra. The study of algebra starts with solving of equations such as polynomials equations.

Algebra and elementary trigonometry is almost a general course to all students of sciences, engineering technology, environmental technology and even in some management courses. Despite its importance, there is high level poor performance in subject area. This paper, study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Performance in mathematics has been a central issue to Mathematics educators (Okeagu, 2013). This poor performance has continued at successive years especially in our schools. Despite the importance of mathematics in science and technology, the issue of poor performance at the end of semester examination becomes a major concern to our academics institutions, which may be as a result of teaching methodology by mathematics teachers/Lecturers. This trend defiles the effort made by Federal Government of Nigeria by making the subject compulsory at all stages of learning (Iiyasu, 2016). In our march toward scientific and technological advancement we need nothing short of good performance in mathematics. Unfortunately, performance of student in mathematics at the end of semester examination has not improved in the past decade. There is dire need for solution to the problem of poor performance in mathematics especially algebra, in order for Nigeria to join the community of developed nations. Iji (2005) has stated that teaching approaches and strategy used in the classrooms by teachers are the root course of this undesirable poor performance in mathematics. Many researchers have carried out investigations on how to remedy the situation. Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this paper, investigate the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the effect of Lecture-Enriched wait-time on academic performance in algebra among polytechnics students.

Research Questions

1. What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

Hypotheses:

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre- test, post-test and post posttest non-equivalent control group design. The essence of pre-test was to determine the academic equivalence of the two groups before the treatment while post-posttest was to determine the performance of the student after the treatment. Pre-test was administered to both sampled polytechnics so as to determine their academic equivalence. The records were kept, then the control group were taught algebra using conventional method of teaching while the experimental group were taught using algebra using Lecture – Enriched Wait - time for eight (8) weeks. Then, post-test was administered to both the control and the experimental groups. The periods for the teaching of each group is two hours per group. This was done by the aid of research assistants who were given a guide on how to handle the classes as well as the wait-time devices in accordance with the Lecture - Enriched wait –time.

The population of the study comprised the two public polytechnics in Cross River State of Nigeria with a total number of 44 National Diploma I students offering algebra at the time that this data was collected. The instrument for this study is Algebraic Performance Test (APT). The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. For the purpose of generating and analyzing data, APT comprises ten (10) essay test questions were developed for the study, which allowed the students to write their understanding on the algebraic concepts.

Presentation of Result

The result of the analysis was used to answer the research question using descriptive statistics while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at alpha $\alpha = 0.05$ level significance.

Research Question 1

What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

This question was answered by determining the mean score between the two groups, using descriptive statistics and the results is as presented in table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of students of experimental and control groups

Group	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD
Experimental	16	13.9	2.8	27	4.3
Control	28	12.6	2.2	19	3.2
Mean difference		1.3		8	
Total	44				

Table 1 shows that the students that were taught with lecture-enriched wait-time method has the highest mean scores of 27 while those taught with traditional lecture method has the minimum mean scores of 19. This shows that the students in the experimental group had some level of improvement as a result of exposure to lecture-enriched wait-time. The standard deviation is an indicative value of wide variability between the scores of the group.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

To test this hypothesis, the pretest and the posttest of each experimental and control groups are analyzed.

Table 2: Wilcoxon sign rank test of mean performance scores of students taught Algebra with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional lecture method

Total number of students (N)	Mean	Var.	t-calculated	t-critical
44	5365.5 1788.5	511.87	-6.99	1.96

Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 shows that the absolute value of t- calculated (6.99) is greater than t- critical (1.96) then we reject H_{01} . thus, it means that there is significant difference between lower achievers taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Discussion of Findings

The research work investigated the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One hypothesis was stated and tested based on lecture – enriched wait – time and Algebra Performance Test (APT) was developed and administered to the sampled groups consisting of 44 students. The collected from the sampled population was analyze using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Analysis of the data collected are presented in table 1 and 2 in accordance with the stated hypothesis. The results of the analyses related to the hypothesis one indicated that, a significant difference exists in the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method. This significant difference found in the performance of students taught algebra was in favor of the experimental group. This is inline with the study of Dalhatu, *et al* (2023) which shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method.

Conclusion

The paper study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. It was shown that better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The use of lecture-enriched wait-time should be encouraged among lecturers teaching algebra more especially at ND level.
2. Government agencies such as Federal and State Ministry of Education, NBTE and other stakeholders in educational sector should organize workshop on lecture-enriched wait-time to all lecturers taking lower level students.

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